

A PARALLEL IMAGE REGISTRATION ARCHITECTURE USING CAM MEMORY

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Abstract

Image Registration usually requires large amount of computation. A similarity counting method using CAM is proposed here to do image registration. This method requires comparisons proportional to the size of the template image, which is much better than the 2-D correlation method or sequential similarity detection method proposed by Barnea. The new algorithm is based on the simultaneous comparison between input signal and the comparant which is a pixel from the template image. A fuzzy comparison using CAM memory is also proposed here. It allows comparison between signals in cells and the comparant with specified tolerance.

Introduction

The Content Addressable Memory (CAM) is a cell structure that has additional logics as compared to regular Random Access Memory (RAM). It is possible to load into and read from the cell as usual. In addition, it is possible to compare the contents of all cells with the content of a comparant simultaneously. Essentially, it is a regular structure parallel in space which can be used to implement many parallel algorithms. The additional logics existing in the cells are comparators. For a systolic array structure the logic associated with the cells can be adders, multipliers, and memory. Obviously, you can think the CAM structure as in between the regular RAM cell and the systolic array cell as far as the function capability is concerned. In this paper a parallel algorithm using CAM is developed to do image registration. This new algorithm can offer image registration with operations on the CAM structure in number much smaller than the traditional approach. This new algorithm also offers fuzzy comparison that means that the template does not have to be exactly the same as the object existing in the searched images. It makes this new algorithm more practical than the conventional approach.

For simplicity to discuss the characteristics of the algorithm, let us consider a one-dimensional situation. To find the template signal $g(x)$ of sequence length M in a signal $f(x)$ of length N , correlation method is usually adopted. To perform the correlation of $g(x)$

with $f(x)$, $L \cdot M$ multiply-add operations are required. Using the proposed similarity counting method in CAM structure only M comparisons are required to obtain the answer. This will be explained in more detail later. For two dimensional image correlation the total complexity of calculations is proportional to the fourth power of the dimension N . Obviously, the computation time required is tediously long. Barnea and Silverman studied this problem and proposed the Sequential Similarity Detection Algorithm (SSDA) in 1972 [1]. Essentially, instead of calculating multiply and add operations for all the points, it calculates the absolute difference for all points and sums up the total. If the template is sufficiently different from the signal, the sum can quickly accumulate to large values. It is even possible to avoid completing the sum operations if the partial result exceeds certain threshold. The algorithm proposed here is derived further from the Barnea's algorithm where absolute difference is not performed. Instead, it is possible to use a CAM structure to do point pair comparisons simultaneously over all pairs in space. If the value of the template is close to the value at a point, the output of the CAM can be considered as a count. Then, the next comparison value from template is loaded into the CAM, and the comparison over all points in space is again activated. By analyzing the sequence of counts it is possible to rearrange and accumulate these counts together. The group of points in space most similar to the template will have the largest count at the end. This kind of similarity counting can achieve the same results as the correlations method and the Sequential Similarity Detection Method. Due to the nature of the operations involved, the proposed method is called similarity counting method.

There are several possible ways to implement the count shuffling and accumulation. One way is to use shift register and adder activated by a controller. The other way can use bit-slice microprocessor with ALU capability. There are some additional shuffling work due to the 2-D template matching operations. For example, in the count accumulation process the shuffling is no longer a simple one position shift. The distance of the shift is dependent on the template spatial extend. The controller

has to be more complicated to handle these situations.

One of the important aspects in the new similarity counting method is based on the capability to do fuzzy comparisons between cell contents and the comparant content. We proposed to use the bit enable mask to achieve this kind of capability. The CAM cells usually have a mask enable register. If some of the bits of the register are set, the comparison between the cells and the comparant at those bits will be activated. It is possible to compare the cells with the template using a certain half tolerance window specified as the less significant bits in the mask register. Two sequential comparisons of this kind with different bits set allows a tolerance window specified around a center value.

Similarity Counting Algorithm:

For simplicity let's start the discussion of a one dimensional problem. The input signal is a sequence $f(x)$, where $x=0, 1, \dots, L-1$. The template signal is a sequence of $g(x)$, where $x=0, 1, \dots, M-1$. Assume that there is no need to worry about the aperiodic correlation. A cyclic correlation of $f(x)$ with $g(x)$ is good enough to indicate the existence of the object in the input.

$$f(x) = f(x), \quad x = 0, 1, \dots, L-1 \quad (1)$$

construct a periodic $g_e(x) = g_e(x+nL)$; where n is an integer.

$$g_e(x) = \begin{cases} g(x), & x = 0, 1, \dots, M-1 \\ 0, & x = M, \dots, L-1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

the periodic correlation is

$$h(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{L-1} f(m)g_e(m+x) \quad (3)$$

Step 1: Shift operation

input sequence $f(0), f(1), f(2), \dots, f(L-1)$
 template sequence
 shifted by one position
 $g(0), g(1), \dots, g(M-1)$

Step 2: Operate and accumulate

$f(0), f(1), f(2) \dots f(L-1)$
 $g(0), g(1) \dots g(M-1)$
 sum: $=P[f(1),g(0)]+P[f(2),g(1)] + \dots$
 $+ P[f(M),g(M-1)]$

where: P is a multiply operator

Step 3: Assign the sum to output sequence $h(x)$
 $h(1) = \text{sum}$

In sequential algorithms the above steps are performed for all the samples in the output sequence. Therefore, there are the M multiply-

add operation in the steps for each output point. A total of $M*L$ multiply-add operation is required to get the correlation sequence. Basically, it is an expansive operation.

If this formulation is extended to a two dimensional input $f(x,y)$ of $L*L$ pixels and a two dimensional template $g(x,y)$ of $M*M$ pixels, the shift operation is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

The "operate and accumulate" will be applied to all the point pairs in the overlapped area between $f(x,y)$ and $g(x,y)$. The accumulated sum is assigned to the output sequence $h(x,y)$. As is obvious that the total operation to obtain $h(x,y)$ is L^2*M^2 multiply and add operations. For an input image of 400×400 pixels and a template image of 56×52 pixels, the correlation required a typical execution time of two to three hours (10,000 sec) approximately on the VAX11/750. At the end, examine all possible local maximum locations in the correlation image plane. Those are the places where the image signal is most similar to the template image. Barnea recognized this computation difficulty and proposed a different operation in step 2 which is less expansive than the multiply. The operation in step 2 of the "sequential similarity detection method" is the absolute difference operation, i.e:

$$P[f(x), g(x+n)] = |f(x) - g(x+n)| \quad (4)$$

Instead of performing multiply, doing absolute difference saves some time. If the image pixel at x is similar to the template pixel at $x+n$, cumulated absolute difference will be small. The original approach of finding the local maximums in the correlation function becomes finding the local minimums in the output image plane. Barnea also recognized that if at a certain position the input image is very different from the template image, the accumulated sum grows quickly. If it exceeds a certain threshold, it is advantageous to abort the "operate and accumulate" step prematurely. Once has improved the algorithm to allow Automatic threshold settings so that the total number of operations performed was further reduced [2].

A new approach called Similarity counting algorithm is proposed here which can allow implementation in parallel hardware. However, the new algorithm can also be implemented in sequential software similar to the similarity

detection method description mentioned above. The operation in step 2 can be generalized to a comparison operation. There can be the exact comparison or the comparison with tolerance. The exact comparison operator P_0 can be defined as:

$$P_0[f(x),g(x+n)] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f(x)=g(x+n) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The comparison operator P_t with tolerance t is then:

$$P_t[f(x),g(x+n)] = \begin{cases} 1, & |f(x)-g(x+n)| \leq t \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

In this approach the operation has been further reduced to a comparison operator that yields binary results. The sum operation is then the counting of the comparison results. Similar to the correlation method, the answer is found to be the local maximums in the output image plane, which is in the opposite situation as the sequential similarity detection method. This approach avoids any algebraic calculations and requires only logical comparisons. If it is implemented in sequential software, it can also have all the advantages proposed in Barnea's and Onoe's techniques. The approach of similarity counting with tolerance should have additional advantages that make the technique more orientation independent and scale independent. From the test results of the simulated algorithm in software evidence shows those advantages. The new approach also allows better registration of images and the template with different gray tone biases. The results showed that if there is prior knowledge or estimate about the tone bias or geometric distortion, it's possible to select an appropriate tolerance to minimize the miss registration in the result. Therefore, the new technique in many respects is comparable or superior to the correlation method and the sequential similarity detection method.

Conclusion

In this paper, the details of this similarity counting method using CAM are discussed. It explains why the new method can achieve much better execution time than the conventional approach. The new method also allows fuzzy comparison between the template and the signal. The comparison counting are merged properly to reach a conclusion. This aspect of merging evidence has a more general context and implication than the application considered here.

References

[1] D. I. Barnea and H. F. Silverman, "A Class of Algorithm for Fast Digital Image Registration" IEEE Trans. on Comp. Vol. C-21, pp. 179-186, Feb. 1972.

[2] M. Onoe and M. Saito, "Automatic Threshold Setting for the Sequential Similarity Detection Algorithm" IEEE Trans. on Comp. pp. 1052-1053, Oct. 1976.